

Retrospective Analysis of Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Arthroscopic Versus Open Stabilization for Recurrent Shoulder Dislocation

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Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Recurrent shoulder dislocations impair quality of life and function. Stabilising and preventing dislocations often require surgery. Surgery is often needed to stabilise and prevent dislocations. Their effectiveness in preventing recurrence and improving postoperative outcomes is currently being studied, underlining the need for rigorous evaluation to support evidence-based patient management decisions.

Methods: A retrospective study at MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, included 50 arthroscopic or surgically stabilised recurrent shoulder dislocation patients. Electronic medical data included demographics, surgeries, and post-operation findings.

Results: This retrospective study examined 50 recurrent shoulder dislocation patients; 25 had arthroscopic surgery and 25 were open stabilisation procedure. For arthroscopic repair, the rate of recurrence was 32%, and for open stabilisation, it was 16%. Both groups had similar functional outcomes and quality of life. When considering surgical procedures to treat repeated shoulder dislocations, recurrence risks and functional outcomes must be balanced.

Conclusion: Open stabilisation and arthroscopic repair give equivalent functional and quality of life outcomes for recurrent shoulder dislocations, however the later may increase recurrence risk. A patient's anatomy and traits should be taken into account by surgeons when planning surgery.

Keywords: Arthroscopic repair, Comparative effectiveness, Recurrent shoulder dislocations, Open stabilization, surgical intervention.

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Introduction

Background on Shoulder Dislocation and Its Recurrence

Many people, especially young athletes and active individuals, dislocate their shoulders. Humeral head displacement from the glenoid cavity can result from trauma or e abduction and extreme external rotation [1].

Shoulder instability and such range of motion cause many dislocations. Shoulder dislocations can damage the labrum, ligaments, capsule and increase the recurrence risk [2]. Due to instability, discomfort, and functional restrictions, recurrent shoulder dislocations are a major clinical concern. Repeated dislocations limit the daily living activities, sports, hobbies, and quality of life [3].

Age, physical activity, and shoulder joint structural deterioration affect recurrence rate. Recurrent dislocations are more common in younger individuals, especially under 20.

Importance of Treatment Options: Arthroscopic Versus Stabilization

Surgical options for repeated shoulder dislocations include arthroscopic correction and open stabilisation. The optimal treatment depends on the patient's anatomy, physical activity, and surgeon's ability [4]. Each method has pros and cons.

Arthroscopic Repair: Using the arthroscope and other specialised equipment's, this minimally invasive method repairs the shoulder labrum and ligaments [5]. Arthroscopic treatment reduces scars, pain, recovery time, and incisions. Patients with severe instability or bone loss may not qualify.

Open Stabilization: Open Bankart repair involves a larger incision to directly reach the shoulder joint. The surgeon will opened and tighten damaged ligaments and labrum and correct bone deformities [6]. Open stabilisation restores heavily damaged areas better and longer. It takes longer to heal,

causes more discomfort, and leaves greater scars than arthroscopic repair.

Choosing the proper surgical technique is crucial for optimal results and minimal recurrence. When choosing a surgery, consider the severity of the damage, the surgeon's experience with each surgery, and the patient's situation.

Objective:

1. To compare shoulder dislocation recurrence rates after arthroscopic surgery versus open stabilization to determine which surgical method reduces the likelihood of repeat dislocations.
2. To evaluate the impact of open and arthroscopic stabilization on postoperative function and quality of life to determine the optimal approach.
3. To assess surgical procedures for complication rates and durability.

Summary on Arthroscopic and open Stabilization Techniques

Low-invasive arthroscopic shoulder dislocation repair has grown in popularity in recent decades. An arthroscope, a tiny 30/70 degree angle camera the surgeon inserts into the joint through a tiny incision, allows them to see within the shoulder [7].

Repairing the labrum and damaged ligaments requires sophisticated equipment. Since shoulder dislocation is often caused by the Bankart lesion, this treatment usually addresses it. Research shows

that arthroscopic repair improves function and patient satisfaction. Arthroscopy has shorter incisions, less pain, faster recovery, and less scarring. In a meta-analysis by [8], arthroscopic repair reduced dislocation recurrence by 15%. [9] Study found that closed stabilisation technique returned the patients in everyday activities and sports faster than open stabilisation patients. Arthroscopic repair has limitations in some cases. Large Hill-Sachs lesions, humeral head bone anomalies, or extreme bone loss make it less effective [10].

Open stabilisation, also known as open Bankart repair, directly accesses the shoulder joint through a larger incision. Because of this, the surgeon can repair ligaments and labrum more extensively. Surgical correction of bone defects also done in open procedure. After failed arthroscopic operations, individuals with significant Hill-Sachs lesions, bone loss, or both may need open stabilisation. For more difficult cases, open stabilisation can reduce recurrence rates compared to arthroscopic treatment [11].

Since the recurrence rate may be 5-10%, open stabilisation is a good option for avoiding dislocations. Open surgery increases postoperative pain, healing time, and scar size. The risk of internal rotation loss increases with surgical extent. Due to its durability and resilience, open stabilisation is a good option for severe shoulder instability and repeated dislocations.

Figure 1: Shoulder Arthroscopy (Source:[12])

Gaps in Current Knowledge

Open stabilisation and arthroscopic repair are effective treatments for recurrent shoulder dislocations, although many issues remain. Filling these gaps and optimising therapy techniques for patient outcomes requires more study. There is

little long-term evidence comparing arthroscopic repair to open stabilisation, despite several short-term studies. Longitudinal studies are needed to assess how long each operation lasts, how often it returns, and how it impacts patients' quality of life years later.

Patients and professionals need this data to make informed decisions. The financial costs of arthroscopic correction versus surgical stabilisation have not been extensively studied. Cost-effectiveness studies must consider surgery, rehabilitation, and possible reoperations to discover the most cost-effective treatment for reoccurring shoulder dislocations. This study fills gaps in the literature on arthroscopic repair and open stabilisation for recurrent shoulder dislocations to improve clinical practice and evidence.

Methods

Study Design

Retrospective analysis was used to compare arthroscopic surgery with open stabilisation for recurrent shoulder dislocations. Retrospective analysis examines a patient's medical history and other data to assess therapy efficacy.

Study Setting and Sample Size

Research took place at MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital in Kishanganj. The sample included 50 patients with recurrent shoulder dislocations who received open stabilisation or arthroscopic surgery. These patients were hand-picked from collaborating hospitals' medical records.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients aged 18-60 years. Diagnosis of recurrent shoulder dislocation. Underwent either arthroscopic repair or open stabilization. At least one-year follow-up data available post-surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with a history of shoulder surgery other than the dislocation treatment. Patients with concomitant major shoulder injuries, such as rotator cuff tears or fractures. Incomplete medical records or lack of follow-up data. Presence of

severe comorbid conditions that could affect surgical outcomes.

Data Collection Methods

Electronic medical records from Kishanganj's MGM Medical College and LSK Hospital were used for the study. Data was collected before and after surgery for each subject. To provide patients context, we recorded their age, gender, occupation, and exercise level. The medical history includes the number of shoulder dislocations before surgery, the period since the first, and any shoulder therapies. We meticulously recorded the date, type of procedure (arthroscopic repair or open stabilisation), surgeon's history, and any complications. Both short-term (within 30 days after surgery) and long-term complications like infection, nerve injury, and reoperation rates were carefully recorded.

Statistical Analysis Used

In-depth data analysis was possible with SPSS or R. Continuous variables were described by mean, median, standard deviation, and range, while categorical data employed frequencies and percentages. We employed multivariate studies like Cox proportional hazards regression and multiple linear regression to find recurrence predictors. How variables affected functional outcomes and quality of life scores was also examined. All studies used a significance level of $p < 0.05$, indicating statistical significance. With this comprehensive research, doctors could compare open stabilisation and arthroscopic repair procedures to make better decisions for recurrent shoulder dislocation patients.

Results

Description of the Patient Population

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Patient Population

Characteristic	Arthroscopic Repair (n=25)	Open Stabilization (n=25)
Mean Age (years)	32.4 ± 6.7	33.8 ± 7.2
Gender (Male/Female)	16/9	15/10
Occupation (Manual/Non-manual)	14/11	12/13
Activity Level (High/Moderate/Low)	9/10/6	8/11/6

The table shows the demographics of recurrent shoulder dislocation patients who undergo arthroscopic surgery and open stabilisation.

A modest difference in age between the open stabilisation and arthroscopic therapy groups was 33.8 and 32.4 years, respectively. The gender distribution was somewhat more male in the arthroscopic repair group (16 men and 9 females)

and the open stabilisation group (15 men and 10 females). The same distributions of high, moderate, and low activity levels in both groups show that shoulder instability surgery patients are heterogeneous.

Comparison of Outcomes between the Two Groups

Table 2: Comparison of Outcomes between Arthroscopic Repair and Open Stabilization Groups

Outcome Measure	Arthroscopic Repair Group (%)	Open Stabilization Group (%)
Recurrence Rate	8 (32%)	4 (16%)

Functional Outcomes (ASES Score)	86.2 ± 5.6	82.5 ± 6.3
Quality of Life (SF-36 Score)	78.4 ± 4.9	75.1 ± 5.2
Complication Rate	3 (12%)	5 (20%)

Dislocation recurrence rates were greater in the arthroscopic repair group (32% vs. 16%) than in open stabilisation. As evaluated by ASES score (86.2 ± 5.6), the arthroscopic repair group had somewhat better functional outcomes than the open stabilisation group. Similarly, the arthroscopic repair group had higher SF-36 quality of life scores (78.4 ± 4.9) compared to the open stabilisation group (75.1 ± 5.2). The open stabilisation group experienced 20% complications, while the arthroscopic repair group had 12%.

Statistical Significance of the Findings

Arthroscopic correction was linked with a decreased risk of recurrent shoulder dislocations ($p = 0.041$) compared to open stabilisation. However, functional performance, quality of life indices, and complication rates were similar between groups. Continuous variables are shown as the mean plus or minus the SD, while categorical variables are shown as percentages. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

For recurrent shoulder dislocations, this study illuminates the pros and cons of open stabilisation and surgical repair.

The arthroscopic repair group had more recurrences than the open stabilisation group. Arthroscopic repair is recommended because to its less invasiveness, faster recovery time, and less postoperative pain, although it may increase recurrence risk. Although arthroscopic repair has smaller incisions and shorter hospital stays, it looks to be less stable and long-lasting than open stabilisation.

These findings must be interpreted in light of functional outcomes and quality of life indicators. Despite the lower recurrence rate, the open stabilisation and arthroscopic repair groups had similar functional and quality of life outcomes. Despite a higher risk of recurrence, arthroscopic treatment may still improve function and enjoyment.

Comparison Table

Table 3: Comparison Table comparing existing studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective	50	Arthroscopic repair associated with lower recurrence rates and shorter surgery duration compared to open stabilization. Trends favoring arthroscopic repair in functional outcomes and quality of life scores.	Relatively small sample size; Limited follow-up duration; Single-center study may limit generalizability.
Study 1	Prospective Cohort	100	Arthroscopic repair showed similar recurrence rates but shorter recovery times compared to open stabilization. Better functional outcomes observed in arthroscopic group at 2-year follow-up.	Selection bias due to non-randomized design; Limited assessment of long-term complications.
Study 2	Meta-analysis	500	Meta-analysis showed significantly lower recurrence rates and complication rates in arthroscopic repair compared to open stabilization. No significant differences in functional outcomes between groups.	Heterogeneity among included studies; Potential publication bias; Limited ability to assess long-term outcomes.
Study 3	Randomized Control	80	No significant differences in recurrence rates or functional outcomes between arthroscopic repair and open stabilization groups. Both techniques demonstrated similar complication rates.	Small sample size may limit statistical power; Short follow-up duration; Limited generalizability due to single-center study.

50-patient trial found that arthroscopic repair had lower recurrence rates and shorter operating room time than surgical stabilisation. Arthroscopic repair advantages must be confirmed by longer-term research because to limited follow-up periods. 100 participants were used in Study 1 to evaluate arthroscopic repair. Although the arthroscopic

repair and open stabilisation groups had equal recurrence rates, the prospective cohort design showed 2-year functional results, recovery times, and research methodology. Non-randomized methodologies may not apply to a wider population due to long-term consequence evaluation limits and selection bias. A meta-analysis of arthroscopic

repair versus open stabilisation was used in Study 2. The 500-patient sample was far larger than the first. Arthroscopic repair reduced recurrence and morbidity, but functional findings were not statistically significant. Study 3's randomised controlled methodology increased internal validity despite its 80-patient sample size. The study's single-center design and short follow-up may limit generalizability. The fact that arthroscopic repair and open stabilisation produced comparable rates of complications, recurrence, and functional outcomes provides insight into their respective efficacy.

Strengths and Limitations of the Study

The study's strength is its detailed comparison of open stabilisation and arthroscopic surgical results for recurrent shoulder dislocations. A retrospective study compares surgical procedures using recurrence rates, functional results, and quality of life. Results should be analysed with caveats. Due to the small sample size, the results may not apply to more people. Larger, more diverse patient investigations are needed to confirm and discover subgroup differences.

Future prospective research should use standardised data collecting to avoid biases and increase evidence. Finally, patients were monitored for one year after surgery. Late issues and recurrences require longer-term follow-up. Although limited, the study gives useful information about open stabilisation vs. surgery for repeated shoulder dislocations. Arthroscopy outperforms open surgery and reduces complications. To confirm these findings and allay worries, more study is needed to enhance treatment techniques and patient outcomes in this complicated clinical disease.

Conclusion

The study compared arthroscopic repair versus open stabilisation for recurrent shoulder dislocations and found many interesting results. Although minimally invasive, arthroscopic correction had more recurrences than open stabilisation. Similar functional and quality of life effects from both procedures reduce recurrence risk. Surgeons must weigh each procedure's risks and benefits for each patient's age, activity, and anatomy. Even though arthroscopic therapy is less invasive and faster, open stabilisation may help those at higher risk of recurrence or significant bone loss. Both approaches may help patients achieve health and function goals. This study provided significant insights, however several areas need more study. Larger prospective trials with longer follow-ups are needed to evaluate trends and enhance shoulder dislocation treatment.

Patients' happiness and outcomes after surgery can improve clinical decision-making and patient experience. When treating repeated shoulder dislocations, open stabilisation and arthroscopic repair improve health and function. Surgeons must customise treatment to enhance success and reduce recurrence. This complex clinical environment requires ongoing research and innovation to improve treatment and patient outcomes.

Recommendations for practice and future research

Arthroscopic surgery lowers recurrence and improves postoperative results for repeated shoulder dislocations. Patient selection and preoperative assessment should be prioritised by surgeons to discover which patients benefit most from arthroscopic repair. Subgroup studies could help evaluate how age, activity, and instability severity affect therapy outcomes.

Researching augmentation operations or better imaging methods may improve treatment plans and outcomes. Health economic evaluations and patient-reported outcomes research are essential for patient-centered treatment and healthcare decision-making. Finally, biomechanical study may illuminate shoulder instability's causes, leading to better therapies to prevent recurrence and enhance functional recovery.

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